
Effectiveness of Shopee Advertisement Version “Ada Shopee, Selalu Di Hati (Prilly & Maxime) (2018)” on Youtube

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ABSTRACT: The presence of social media has a positive impact, especially on communication in all fields. It affects the shift from conventional to modern communication styles, which becomes more efficient and effective. This is a study that aims to measure how much the AISAS (*Attention, Interest, Search, Action, Share*) model influences consumer behavior towards the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, selalu di hati" version of Prilly & Maxime, which was broadcast on YouTube. The study used a quantitative method with 80 research subjects from the Informatics Study Program Morning Class at Indraprasta University in 2015. Furthermore, the existing data were processed using SPSS 17.0. Validity was tested by correcting the total item correlation with a score above 0.30. Overall, the results of this study indicate that this advertisement successfully influences consumer behavior that is highly involved with the AISAS model.

KEYWORDS: Ad Effectiveness; AISAS Model; Shopee; E-Commerce; Communication.

1. INTRODUCTION

The development of technology in Indonesia is rapidly advancing in human life, and all of this is unavoidable. There are various types of technology with advanced features that make it easier for people to communicate with each other. Communication media, or what is now known as social media, is the most rapidly changing medium, as stated by Kaplan and Haenlein (in Lesmana, 2019). Social media is a collection of internet-based applications used to create or share content. These applications are created and distributed by users based on the ideology and technology of Web 2.0.

The sophistication of technology makes a country more advanced, and people are required to create innovations and creativity that increasingly ease human life, one of which is the ease of meeting all human needs. Business operators market their ventures through unique, creative, and non-mainstream communication methods. The company interprets communication for business purposes in the form of advertisements. Advertisements themselves are also a communication tool aimed at explaining, describing, and conveying messages about a product to the public, with the goal of making the public aware of the product and wanting to have, own, and buy the product. Business actors compete to create advertisements that are creative and innovative so that the ads are always easy to remember. In general, advertising is a message intended to persuade people to be able and interested in buying (Jefkins, 1997).

The presence of the right marketing communication components influences attractive advertisements. Furthermore, Wenats (2012) states that marketing communication consists of four points of the marketing mix: product, place, price, and promotion. So, marketing communication is part of strengthening the marketing strategy to achieve broad and desired segmentation.

There are several ways to attract customers' attention. The first is *hard sell*, which focuses on direct marketing messages. The second is *soft sell*, which promotes products gradually and indirectly (Susilo, 2009). Researchers can conclude that the content of an advertisement significantly influences curiosity, interest, and the desire to purchase the product. Furthermore, the effectiveness of an advertisement can be seen in how the audience responds to receiving the advertisement message and their actions to purchase the advertised product. The researcher will discuss the effectiveness of the Shopee TV commercial message "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" version Prilly & Maxime on YouTube among the 2015 batch students of the Morning Class Informatics Study Program at Indraprastha University (UNINDRA).

Shopee arrived in Indonesia at the end of May 2015 and started operating in other countries at the end of June 2015. In addition, Shopee has been operating in Thailand, Malaysia, the Philippines, Singapore, and Vietnam. In addition to offering integrated logistics arrangements and secure payment processes, Shopee makes sales easier. Most of Shopee Indonesia's consumer demographics are women, especially schoolgirls, university students, and housewives.

In the Shopee ad version "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)", it uses a romantic and humorous theme and also features public figures Prilly and Maxime. This advertisement contains romantic themes and elements, and it has a duration of approximately 30 seconds.

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Based on the advertisement, the researchers assess that the concept of this ad indeed uses the appeal of the "Baby Shark" song, which has been adapted into a Shopee version containing lines promoting Shopee. This research was conducted to understand attention, interest, search, action, and provide information due to the Shopee advertisement "Baby Shark, Buy Everything on Shopee with Free Shipping."

The effectiveness of advertising strategies has been extensively researched across various media and industries, revealing important insights into how different approaches influence consumer behavior. This literature review summarizes findings from research focusing on below-the-line (BTL) advertising, digital media and social media platforms, advertising effectiveness, and the AISAS Theory to provide a comprehensive understanding in this study.

Below-the-Line (BTL) Advertising

Advertising, according to Kotler (2002: 658), is defined as the dissemination and promotion of ideas, goods, or services indirectly to the necessary sponsors (Jaiz, 2014). Wijoyo, et al. (2018) studied BTL advertising at Rumah Sakit Nasional Surabaya, highlighting the effectiveness of physical media such as brochures, posters, and x-banners. This study uses the Customer Response Index to evaluate consumer awareness, understanding, interest, intention, and action.

The results show that brochures and x-banners are effective at all stages of the CRI, while posters are more effective in increasing awareness and intention. The effectiveness of these physical media can be attributed to their ability to reach the audience directly, especially in relevant environments such as hospitals. However, sustainability and production costs are challenges that need to be considered.

Indrawati, et al. (2017) emphasize the use of the EPIC model in promoting Krisna Oleh-Oleh Khas Bali through social media, showing how communication and empathy can enhance brand awareness and purchasing decisions, especially among the younger generation. These results provide insight that although social media is very popular, strategies involving an emotional approach remain important to attract customer attention.

Digital Media and Social Media Platforms Social Media

Cendriyansyah and Trenggana (2019) analyzed the role of Instagram in building emotional connections with customers at Eduplex Coworking Bandung. With an average EPIC effectiveness score of 3.75, this study highlights the platform's ability to build relationships, although the aspects of persuasion and communication need to be improved. This analysis highlights the challenge of maintaining consumer attention amidst the abundance of competing digital content.

Halim, et al. (2019) also studied email marketing in the Indonesian travel industry, finding that high-quality information and entertainment increase engagement, while transparency and reducing intrusive nature are crucial to addressing negative perceptions. This research shows that message personalization can be a solution to enhance the effectiveness of email marketing.

The role of social media was also studied by Indrawati, et al. (2017), who found that platforms like Facebook and Instagram are effective and cost-efficient in promoting tourism-related products. They noted an average EPIC score of 3.87, emphasizing the importance of empathetic communication in attracting a young audience. This underscores the potential of social media as a flexible tool to reach various market segments.

Effectiveness of Advertising

Effective advertising is very important for selling goods or services. It is very difficult to measure how effective a business is without it. Advertisements are considered effective when their objectives are achieved. Advertisements created by the company must be able to inform, persuade, and remind consumers about the products it offers through advertising media. According to Purnama (2001).

Fitriana's study (2013) shows how brand image mediates the relationship between advertising effectiveness and purchase intention. Effective advertising not only directly influences purchasing behavior but also enhances brand perception. This dual impact highlights the strategic value of consistent and engaging content. In this context, brands must consider the synergy between a strong brand image and creative elements in their advertisements. Meanwhile, Dinda, et al. (2018) evaluated Traveloka's YouTube advertisement, finding its effectiveness with an EPIC score of 3.89. YouTube, which has more than one billion users, is one of the most popular types of video-based social media lately (Juitania & Indrawan, 2020). The platform's extensive reach and demographic alignment with digital users enhance the campaign's impact, although improvements are needed in the dimensions of persuasion and communication. This research highlights the important role of digital platforms in reducing costs and reaching a wider market.

2. METHODOLOGY

This research discusses the "effectiveness of the Shopee advertisement "There is Shopee, always in the heart (2018)" version by Prilly & Maxime according to students of Universitas Indraprasta. The effectiveness of an advertisement greatly influences the sales of the product. The researcher used a quantitative method in this study. According to Kriyantono (2008:50), Quantitative research is a type of research that describes or explains a problem and produces findings that can be used for general purposes. In quantitative

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research, researchers must remain objective and not be influenced by the data; in other words, they should not restrict concepts or data measurement tools according to their preferences. This research aims to provide an explanation regarding a phenomenon discussed by the researchers, namely the extent of Attention, Interest, Search, Action, and Share from the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" version by Prilly & Maxime among students of Universitas Indraprasta.

In this study, the researcher used a population of 400 students from the Informatics Program, Class of 2015, Morning Class, Universitas Indraprasta, who are actively enrolled in the odd semester. The researcher randomly determined the population that would become the cluster sample of students who are aware of and interested in the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, selalu di hati" version Prilly & Maxime (2018). The researcher used 80 respondents with purposive sampling technique.

3. RESEARCH FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The researchers chose the subjects of this study to be students from the Faculty of Computer Science, Informatics Program, morning class of 2015, at Indraprasta University. This study involves 80 male and female students (random). Determine the number of respondents based on the consideration of the sample size according to the requirements of good statistical calculations (using the Slovin formula). For the purpose of this research, the researcher used purposive sampling technique with the Slovin formula to select participants (Kriyantono, 2009).

Reliability Test

Tabel 1

Reliability Test Variable of Advertising Effectiveness

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.909	23

Based on the table above, we found that the Cronbach's alpha value for the questionnaire statements on the advertising effectiveness variable distributed to 30 respondents for the pre-test is 0.909, which means that the tested variable can be considered reliable if the alpha value is more than 0.6, which means that the variable can be considered reliable if the alpha value is more than 0.6.

Validity Test

The correlation coefficient method is used to test the validity of a question. This means correlating the score of each question with its total score. If the correlation value is positive and the calculated r is greater than 0.3, then the question is considered valid. To test the validity of each question in the questionnaire, the researcher conducted a pre-test to evaluate the validity level of the statement instrument, and the researcher distributed the questionnaire to 30 respondents via Google Docs. Here are the results of the validity test conducted using SPSS 17.0.

Validity Test

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
I know that the Shopee ad "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" featuring Prilly & Maxime has a romantic theme.	61.62	86.672	.709	.901

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I know that the Shopee ad "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" featuring Prilly & Maxime uses humor.	61.45	91.256	.481	.906
I know the lyrics to the Baby Shark song from the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" version by Prilly & Maxime.	61.10	89.025	.415	.909
I know the tagline from the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" version by Prilly & Maxime.	61.41	87.180	.630	.903
I know that the Shopee ad "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" featuring Prilly & Maxime offers a variety of products.	61.03	92.534	.309	.910
I am interested in the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" version by Prilly & Maxime because it showcases the romantic side of the relationship between Prilly & Maxime.	61.69	88.865	.537	.905

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I am interested in the Shopee ad "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" version by Prilly & Maxime because it features a story that contains humor.	61.69	84.579	.762	.900
I am interested in the lyrics of the Shopee version of Baby Shark because they are easy to remember.	60.93	93.924	.362	.910
I am interested in the Shopee ad tagline "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" by Prilly & Maxime because it is easy to understand.	61.41	87.680	.692	.902
I became interested in Shopee products after seeing the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" featuring Prilly & Maxime.	61.52	85.616	.759	.900
I am looking for information about the products offered by Shopee after seeing the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" version by Prilly & Maxime.	61.31	87.079	.639	.903
I am looking for feedback on the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" featuring Prilly & Maxime.	61.62	83.601	.751	.900

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I am looking for information about the continuation of the Shopee ad "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" version Prilly & Maxime, which uses the same endorser, but with a different theme.	61.59	88.823	.511	.906
I am looking for information about the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, Selalu di hati (2018)" featuring Prilly & Maxime that was published in the media, besides television.	61.79	85.241	.720	.901
I am looking for product reviews on Shopee before buying the product I want.	60.90	93.667	.344	.910
I am looking for a comparison of the product in terms of the prices offered by Shopee and those offered by other e-commerce platforms.	61.14	95.337	.377	.914
I am looking for a comparison of the product quality offered by Shopee and other e-commerce platforms.	61.07	97.995	.326	.916
I bought the products I needed through Shopee after seeing the advertisement.	61.69	88.436	.617	.904

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I only use Shopee for online shopping.	61.72	88.350	.428	.909
I am sharing a positive experience of purchasing products I like using Shopee's services.	61.31	86.222	.702	.901
I respond to comments from Shopee users on social media.	61.55	87.970	.577	.904
I promote Shopee's services through Word Of Mouth (WOM) to my friends.	61.59	87.823	.744	.902
I invited my friends to use Shopee's services for online shopping.	61.41	89.323	.513	.906

In table 3.4 above, information is obtained regarding the Corrected Item-Total Correlation values on the questionnaire statements of the message effectiveness variable distributed to 30 pre-test respondents. The question is considered valid if the calculated $r > 0.3$. As shown in table 3.4 above, it is known that the calculated r (Corrected Item –Total Correlation) overall is more than 0.3. Thus, it can be concluded that out of the 24 statements in the message effectiveness variable questionnaire, overall, they are considered valid.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on what has been discussed in the results of this research, the researcher found answers to the problem identification expressed in chapter 1 along with the problem formulation being discussed in this study. The main focus of this research is to determine the effectiveness of the Shopee advertisement "Ada Shopee, selalu di hati" created by Prilly Latuconsina and Maxime Bouttier on YouTube, using the AISAS theory (Attention, Interest, Search, Action, Share) related to the statements in the questionnaire.

With the emergence of social media as part of the advancement of information and communication technology, they have changed the way people communicate. Based on the research conducted by the researcher, advertisements on YouTube have a significantly high level of effectiveness besides on television, because now everyone has gadgets, making it easier for them to access YouTube wherever they are.

In fact, the presence of social media has had a positive impact, especially on communication in all fields, such as political communication, mass communication, and interpersonal communication. Social media has also changed the way we communicate from conventional to modern and digital, making communication more effective and efficient.

The results of this research analysis are supported by a descriptive research method. With the research subjects being students of the Faculty of Computer Science, Informatics Study Program, Indraprastha University, Morning Class, batch of 2015, totaling 80 people. Meanwhile, the sampling technique used is purposive sampling. Data were collected through quantitative analysis and interpretation after the distribution of questionnaires to respondents and literature review from previous studies.

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